

COMPARISON BETWEEN TRC AND CFRP AS EXTERNAL REINFORCEMENT FOR PLAIN CONCRETE BEAMS

S. Verbruggen^{1*}, J. Wastiels¹, T. Tysmans¹, S. Puystiens¹

¹ Department of Mechanics of Materials and Constructions, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels, Belgium

* Corresponding author (svetlana.verbruggen@vub.ac.be)

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ABSTRACT

Strengthening and repairing existing structures is often more economical and sustainable than demolishing and afterwards rebuilding them. Concrete structures can be strengthened using high performance glass fibre Textile Reinforced Cements (TRC) as an external reinforcement. Until now no evaluation of the cracking behaviour of this system with respect to the established technique of CFRP strips is reported. This paper presents the experimental comparison between both techniques, based on four point bending tests with third point loading, where the crack pattern evolution is monitored with Digital Image Correlation (DIC). A wider TRC external reinforcement restrains the high initial stiffness up to a higher load and reduces the crack widths in comparison with the CFRP solution, designed to meet an equal failure load. These advantages can be attributed to the crack bridging capacity of the external reinforcement.

1 Introduction

The growing urbanization together with the awareness on reducing carbon emission, originating from the construction industry, increases the need for strengthening and repair of the existing buildings and infrastructure, in disfavour of new construction. Several strengthening and repair systems for steel reinforced concrete structures are currently commercially available; one of the most common systems is the externally bonded Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) strip. For this application most often carbon fibres are embedded in an epoxy matrix (CFRP) [1, 2]. Despite of the numerous successful applications of the CFRP system there is still a strong need for improvements concerning the heat resistance, fire safety and high cost. The use of a TRC could possibly offer an answer to these needs, where the cementitious matrix material is heat resistant and fire safe and the E-glass fibres are less expensive compared to the carbon fibres.

Cementitious materials are stiff and strong materials in compression, but they are characterized by a low tensile strength and a brittle behaviour. Therefore these materials need to be reinforced with traditional steel reinforcement or, alternatively with fibres. Until now most studies concerning fibre reinforcement for concrete concentrated on discontinuous fibre structures, which can increase the ductility but hardly or not the tensile strength [3, 4]. If one wants to create a ductile cement matrix composite with an increased tensile strength, a dense and continuous fibre structure such as fibre textiles should be used, leading to a Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC).

Cost effective E-glass fibres are often used in the composites industry. An important drawback however of these fibres in combination with a cementitious matrix is the reduction of their performance with time, due to the alkaline environment of an ordinary concrete or mortar [5] and to portlandite deposition. In order to avoid fibre degradation the Vrije Universiteit Brussel developed an Inorganic Phosphate Cement (IPC) [6], which is acidic in fresh state, but neutral after hardening. The time of the acidic phase is sufficiently short not to degrade the properties of the glass fibres. Its relatively small grain size (between 10 and 100 μm) moreover enables to impregnate dense textiles up to high fibre volume fractions (up to 25 % in volume [7]). As a result, a durable cementitious composite with high tensile (up to 60 MPa for IPC reinforced with randomly oriented glass fibre textiles) and compressive (80 MPa) capacities and which is heat- and fire resistant (highest European class A1), is created, what makes it appropriate for structural applications. The tensile behaviour of glass fibre reinforced IPC (IPC TRC) is nonlinear and consists of 3 zones: the first linear elastic zone, where fibres and matrix are working together; a second zone where the matrix cracks; and finally a second linear zone where only the fibres contribute to the strength and stiffness of the TRC. [8]

Recently there is an increased interest in the use TRC's for structural applications like stay-in-place formwork [9, 10] and strengthening and repair of concrete structures [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Especially IPC TRC has already proven its capabilities as a material for structural stay-in-place formwork [16, 17, 18] and external strengthening [19] of concrete beams. These studies revealed that the initial uncracked stiffness of the concrete beam is retained far above the calculated and measured cracking moment. This increased stiffness can be very interesting in cases where the serviceability limit state of deflection is governing the (re)design. However no validation concerning the cracking behaviour has been presented compared to the existing techniques like external CFRP reinforcement. Moreover only few studies have investigated the general influence of an externally bonded reinforcement on the crack pattern of the concrete beam [20, 21]. Therefore this paper compares the behaviour of plain concrete beams externally reinforced with a standard full-width IPC TRC strip, a CFRP strip designed to meet the same failure load and a CFRP strip with the same width as the IPC TRC. This comparison is based on four point bending tests with third point loading, which are monitored with Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to follow the crack pattern evolution.

2 Experimental program

2.1 Specimen types

To compare the effects of external reinforcement made of IPC TRC and CFRP on the load bearing behaviour and on the crack pattern evolution of a plain concrete beam, 4 specimen types are designed and subjected to a four point bending test with third point loading. The reinforcing material, the width of this reinforcement and the application method are varied, resulting in the following specimens (Tab. 1):

1. IPC TRC – full width – glued
2. IPC TRC – full width – glued and bolted
3. CFRP – 14 mm – glued
4. CFRP – full width – glued

The beams have a total length of 650 mm, a distance between the supports of 600 mm, and a nominal height and width of 95 mm and 70 mm. The IPC TRC reinforced beams are strengthened by gluing a strip made of IPC reinforced with 8 glass fibre mat layers of 300 g/m² (resulting in a nominal thickness

of 4 mm) over the entire tensioned lower surface of the beam (type 1 in Tab. 1). For the CFRP reinforced beams, a CFRP strip with a standard thickness of 1.2 mm is glued underneath the concrete. For one beam type, the CFRP covers the whole width of the beam (type 4 in Tab. 1). Another one has a strip of 14 mm wide (type 3 in Tab. 1), so as to obtain the same ultimate load as the IPC TRC reinforced beam, following the FIB bulletin 14 [1]. Before gluing the reinforcement to the beams, the concrete surface layer of around 10 mm is removed with a diamond saw such that the granulates are reached for all beams. The external reinforcement is bonded onto the concrete with a two-component epoxy glue (PC 5800/BL [22]), which is also commercially used for the gluing of CFRP reinforcement strips. Given previous experiences [19], an extra beam type was tested where two additional bolt connections were applied to avoid peeling-off of the IPC TRC reinforcement (type 2 in Tab. 1). This connection is made (after the glue hardened) by fixing a thread rod (\varnothing 12 mm) using a chemical anchor. The nuts are tightened up to 15 Nm. Such a connection is impossible for the CFRP, due to the aligned fibre structure.

2.2 Test set-up

The above mentioned specimen types are tested under four point bending test with third point loading (Fig. 1). The loading is displacement controlled with a displacement rate of 0.2 mm/min, using a servo-hydraulic actuator (Instron 5885H).

During the bending test the behaviour of the beams is monitored using a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT) placed in the middle of the span underneath the beam. The crack pattern evolution is followed using the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique [23], which is a non-contacting optical measuring technique. Displacements can be measured by the comparison of subsequent surface pictures taken from a speckle pattern of black spots on a white background, which is applied on the specimens. Out of the displacement field, the strains can be calculated. One pair of cameras follows the side of the beam and another pair of cameras the bottom. Both systems are able to measure a window of approximately 200 mm length in the middle of the beam, where the bending moment is constant.

2.3 Used materials

2.3.1 Concrete

To simulate the conditions of an old building consisting of damaged beams or beams with insufficient loadbearing capacity, a low strength concrete is designed with following mass proportions:

- 220 kg Portland cement CEM II 32.5N
- 80 kg fly ash
- 165 l water
- 482 kg sand (0/2)
- 482 kg gravel (4/6)
- 896 kg gravel (6.5/14)

Tab. 2 shows the mean material characteristics after 14 days of age, which is the testing age of the beams. Due to the low strength mixture, the scatter on the material characteristics is significant (up to 5 %).

The compressive strength is the cylindrical strength calculated from tests performed on cubic specimens, with sides of approximately 100 mm. This calculation is based on [24].

2.3.2 IPC TRC

The matrix material IPC is mixed in the mass proportions of:

- 1 liquid component
- 0.82 high performance powder

The glass fibres used are randomly oriented in-plane chopped strand mats Vetrotex M5, with a mass of 300 g/m². The laminates consist of 8 layers of these fibre mats, resulting in a fibre volume fraction of 22 % and in the mean material characteristics shown in Tab. 3.

2.3.3 CFRP

A commercially available CFRP strip is used [25], on which only one tensile test is performed, resulting in a tensile strength of 2210 MPa and a Youngs modulus of 143 GPa.

3 Experimental results

This section first compares the analytical and experimental results concerning the cracking moment of the reinforced beams. Hereafter the load

deflection curves of the IPC TRC and CFRP reinforcement systems are compared based on the cracking moment and failure load. Finally the DIC data are analysed, resulting in a comparison of the crack patterns and their evolution for both reinforcing systems.

3.1 Analytical versus experimental results

Fig. 2 represents the load-deflection curves of the four point bending tests performed on the different beam types. The curved lines represent the experimental measured evolution, while the horizontal line indicates the average analytically calculated cracking moment. A zoom of the curves, for loads from 0 kN to 7 kN and for deflections from 0 mm to 0.5 mm is given in the lower right corner.

The observation of an apparent increased cracking moment due to the application of externally bonded reinforcement on a concrete beam, as discussed for IPC TRC in [16, 17, 18, 19], is confirmed by Fig. 2. Both IPC TRC reinforced beams (type 1 and 2) keep their initial stiffness up to a load of 6 kN (instead of the analytically calculated 3 kN, or an increase of 100 %); the CFRP reinforced beams of type 3 and 4 retain their stiffness up to 4 kN and 20 kN respectively (increase of 33 % and 567 %). This apparent raise in cracking moment causes an upward shift of the second part of the load-deflection curve, resulting in a lower deflection than calculated for the same applied load. This shift may be useful in cases where the serviceability limit state of deflection is governing.

The conservation of initial high stiffness shows to be independent of the use of extra anchorage mechanisms for the IPC TRC reinforced beams, as beam type 1 and 2 both reduce in stiffness at an equal load (6 kN).

3.2 Load-bearing behaviour of IPC TRC versus CFRP reinforced beams

Using the stiffer and stronger CFRP reinforcing material with the same contact area results in stiffness conservation up to a 200 % higher load. Using however the same stiff and strong CFRP, but with a reduced width (14 mm instead of 70 mm) designed to achieve the same ultimate load as the IPC TRC reinforced beams, the apparent gain in cracking moment is only one third (33 %) of the one achieved with IPC TRC (100 %). This observation

indicates that the raise is highly dependent on the contact area between the reinforcement and the concrete. Covering the entire tensile face thus appears to better hinder the crack extension and opening.

Both simply glued beams (type 1 and 3) fail at 10.5 kN, which is significantly lower than the calculated failure load of 15 kN (calculation based on [1]). The type 4 beam also does not reach the calculated failure load of 26 kN. The failure mode for these three beams is premature peeling-off of the external reinforcement. Only beam 2, with additional bolted end connections, fails in the designed favourable failure mode of concrete crushing and IPC TRC in tension. Apart from this failure mode, beam 2 is also the only one capable of reaching the calculated ultimate load. This confirms the conclusions drawn in [19], that additional bolt connections are needed to fail at the designed load and in a favourable way.

The above findings indicate that for an equal loadbearing capacity, the wider IPC TRC reinforcement (types 1 and 2) is more effective than the narrow CFRP one (type 3).

3.3 Cracking behaviour

Based on the DIC results, a comparison between the cracking behaviour of a concrete beam reinforced with IPC TRC and with CFRP is made.

Fig. 3 shows the horizontal displacement (Y-axis) versus the horizontal position on the beam (X-axis), both expressed in mm, for different load steps. The curves are obtained by extracting the DIC data over a full line with 2000 points, drawn over the entire visible width, as close as possible to the bottom but still in the concrete area. The vertical discontinuities indicate a sudden increase in displacement, and thus a crack in the concrete. A crack is defined at the maximum load as a difference in horizontal displacement bigger than 0.02 mm over a horizontal interval of 5 mm, and that is not adjacent to another crack interval. An overview of the plotted cracks and their numbering is given in the top left corner of each graph. This overview is based on the strain field of the beam at its maximum load. The purple colour represents a negative or zero strain field, and the more the colour evolves to red tones the higher the strain becomes. The red zones, representing a strain of 1 % or higher, indicate the cracks.

The conclusions concerning the cracking moment drawn from Fig. 2 are confirmed by Fig. 3: the larger the contact surface between concrete and external reinforcement, the more effective the external reinforcement works. Only beam type 3 (14 mm wide contact area) exhibits already clear discontinuities at a load of 5 kN. This beam type is also the only one that hardly forms 3 cracks, versus at least 6 cracks for the other beam types. Moreover, the cracks of beam 3 open clearly more wide than the other beams (maximum crack width of 0.85 mm for beam 3 versus max 0.5 mm for beams 1, 2 and 4).

At a comparable load step of 10 kN both IPC TRC reinforced beams and the beam type 4 exhibit more or less the same amount of cracks (6 cracks). Exceeding this load, it is clear for the IPC TRC reinforced beam of type 2 that 3 extra cracks are developed, meaning that the external reinforcement enables the nucleation of extra secondary cracks rather than developing the existing ones. Due to the very high strength and stiffness of the CFRP strip the crack widths for beam type 4 remain very small over the entire loading process.

The evolution of the crack widths with an increasing load is given in Fig. 4. All cracks present in the beams are represented and indicated with the same numbering as in Fig. 3. To clarify the onset of the crack development, the upper right corner shows a zoom in this curve for loads from 3 kN to 7 kN and crack widths from 0 mm to 0.02 mm. In all graphs the relapse of the curve after the maximum load is reached, is left out to preserve the overview.

Fig. 4 indicates that all beam types exhibit already the beginning of at least one crack at a load less than 5 kN, even when the initial high stiffness does not reduce up to a higher load, as discussed for Fig. 2. This leads to the conclusion that the raise in cracking moment in Fig. 2 is only an apparent retardation, as the stiffness is retained but the cracks actually initiate. For beam types 1, 2 and 4, the crack growth is a gradual and slow process. This is in contrast with beam type 3, where the cracks even reveal a horizontal plateau at a load of 4 kN, meaning that the crack width increases without an increase in load. The latter corresponds with only a limited apparent increase in cracking moment (33 %), this in contrast to the other beam types, where respectively 100 % is reached for types 1 and 2 and 567 % for type 4.

Fig. 5 gives an overview of the strain fields in the central parts of the beams, measured at the side (upper row) and the bottom (lower row), at both a load of 10 kN and the maximum load. An identical strain scale as the overviews in Fig. 3 is used. By the nature of the measuring technique only surface properties can be measured. This implies that for the bottom side only the strains of the external reinforcement are visualized and not the properties of the concrete or glue underneath it.

Fig. 5 clearly indicates that the localized strains in the concrete that are visible at the side of the beams, corresponding to cracks, are spread over the whole length of the external reinforcement. The external reinforcement thus possesses a crack bridging capacity, which may explain the preservation of the beam's initial stiffness and the apparent retardation of the cracking moment. As the contact area is lower for beam type 3 and as this probably influences the crack bridging capacity in an unfavourable way, it might explain that the initial stiffness of this beam is retained less long than the one of the other beam types.

4 Conclusions

Comparative four point bending tests with third point loading on small scale concrete beams with external reinforcement made of CFRP on the one hand and IPC TRC on the other hand, show that the high initial stiffness of the beam is conserved long after cracks nucleate. The preservation of the stiffness is independent on the anchorage mechanism, but it increases with an increasing strength and stiffness of the external reinforcement and it decreases with a decreasing contact area. This smaller contact area also results in a lower amount of cracks with a bigger total crack opening, which is detrimental for the moisture penetration and thus durability of the inner steel reinforcement. A possible explanation for these phenomena can be found in the crack bridging capacity of the external reinforcement. When designing for an equal failure load, the wider IPC TRC reinforcement assures a retention of the high initial stiffness up to a higher load and reduced crack widths with reference to the CFRP solution.

The application of IPC TRC as an external reinforcement material enables the application of extra bolt connections. Using bolts as an extra

anchorage results in a more favourable failure mode of concrete crushing and IPC TRC in tension, instead of the brittle failure due to peeling-off of the external reinforcement.

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Tab.1. 4 beam types were made.

Beam type #	Reinforcement material	width	Connection
1	IPC TRC	Full	Glued
2	IPC TRC	Full	Glued and bolted
3	CFRP	14 mm	Glued
4	CFRP	Full	Glued

Tab.2. Mean material characteristics concrete after 14 days of age, which is the testing age of the beams.

Compressive strength	16.8 MPa
Young modulus	28.2 GPa
Modulus of rupture	3.5 MPa

Tab.3. Mean material characteristics glass fibre reinforced IPC TRC.

Tensile strength	67.9 MPa
Young modulus stage I	21.0 GPa
Young modulus stage III	4.7 GPa

Fig.1. A four point bending test with third point load is performed on the externally reinforced beams.

Fig.2. The load-deflection curves indicate that the initial uncracked beam stiffness is retained to significantly higher loads than calculated (dotted line at 3 kN) for all four beam types.

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Fig.3. The horizontal displacement curves and strain fields show that only beam type 3 exhibits only 3 cracks which grow wider than the other beams and that higher failure load enable the nucleation of new cracks.

Fig.4. For all beam types cracks nucleate at a load less than 5 kN, but except for beam type 3 the cracks do not grow significantly until a much higher load is applied.

Fig.5. The uniform strain field in the external reinforcement indicates a crack bridging capacity.

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